

The Effects of Green Brand Knowledge in Purchase Intention (Case Study from Indonesia)

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

Lately, products concerning environmental sustainability are emerging in Indonesia. Many companies are involved in various forms of green marketing activities as part of their strategy. Among them is AQUALife. AQUALife is a brand of mineral water that is bottled in recycled plastic bottles. As of this research, AQUALife is only exclusively available in Bali.

Considering the strong brand image of AQUA, it has drawn interest to compare and analyze the brand knowledge within green (environmentally friendly) areas of AQUALife of respondents in Bali, where the product exists and Bandung where the product is not available. Furthermore, this study also attempts to see whether the green brand knowledge has correlation with the purchase intention towards AQUALife.

Questionnaires were distributed to 200 respondents coming from Bali and Bandung, and the data were processed using several tests to be analyzed. The result shows that the green brand knowledge of respondents from Bali and Bandung are within 3,36 range or moderate. The green brand knowledge of AQUALife in Bandung has a high correlation to the purchasing intention, and it has affected 79.7% to purchasing intention. The green brand knowledge of AQUALife in Bali has a high correlation to the purchasing intention, and it has affected 80.7% to purchasing intention. After further research, there is indeed a link between green brand knowledge and purchase intention. However, to see the success of green marketing used by AQUALife, we can say its success rate is low. Since the result of the analysis from the responses from the respondents of Bali and Bandung is similar.

Keywords: BRAND AWARENESS, BRAND IMAGE, GREEN BRAND KNOWLEDGE, PURCHASE INTENTION

Introduction

According to research conducted by Jenna R. Jambeck¹, up to the year of 2010, around 3.22 tons of plastic waste have been found across the Indonesian coast. Even though back in 2008 the Indonesian government issued the law regarding waste management, it didn't change the situation much due to the lack of awareness by the people. The waste management law of 2008 (No.18/2008) was made by the government to manage the waste disposal process for the country, but according to Indonesia's statistics bureau, there are at least 66.8 Indonesian that burn out their waste as of 2018. The waste management activities and processes in Indonesia

can be considered really bad as of now. According to the chief director of Indonesia Plastic Bag Diet Movement (GIDKP)², currently Indonesia is only able to recycle plastic waste for around 9%. If we count it back to the research done by Jenna R. Jambeck¹ then there would only be around 263 kilos of plastic waste recycled by Indonesia. Most of those plastic waste are disposed of irresponsibly even causing the death of a whale at the coast of Wakatobi beach, Southeast Sulawesi where 5.9 kilos plastic waste was found inside its belly. Up to the year 2018, Indonesia became the second largest country in the world in terms of waste just next to China standing in the first place³.

There are some marketing activities that could be done to anticipate the ever growing environmental problem in the sense of plastic waste. One of the mentioned marketing activities to resolve this problem is called green marketing which revolves around a better environment. Green marketing itself is widely known as a promotion process done for a product made solely to monitor the environment⁴. Numerous restaurants across the globe have been implementing this strategy by creating environmentally friendly straws or even raising a straw-free movement. In Indonesia, these kinds of activities are also done by McDonalds since late 2018⁵. Other examples come from BOGA Group which is the head company that is responsible for many restaurants such as Pepper Lunch, Bakerzin, etc have been selling bamboo based straws to preserve the environment⁶. The bottled water activities done by Ades are also doing this movement by creating the eco crushed bottle back in 2012⁷. These bottles created by Ades were made using less plastic composition and also easier to crush which later led to less waste volume.

AQUA is known to be the leading brand in Indonesia dominating all bottled water sales in 2018 according to Tempo. They are so big that the difference in terms of other brands to them reach to the margins of 46.7%⁸. Currently there are around 500 companies which are competing in the bottled water industry. AQUA itself has been the pioneer in producing recycled products since 1993 with the program "AQUA Peduli"⁹. In February 2019, AQUA which is a bottled water brand produced by Danone, launched a bottled drink product that is packed inside the recycled PET packaging. This product was first launched in Bali, Indonesia and was widely known as AQUALife. The AQUA water bottle generally used 25% of recycled PET in its production. So with that being said the AQUALife which is now using 100% of recycled matters is considered to be one of AQUA's response to the environmental problem right now.

With AQUA dominating around 46.7% of the bottled water market, consumers are considered to be aware of the general information regarding the product. Information and knowledge regarding the product will be a key factor in the later buying process. The more you know about the product then the better and closer for society to understand about the product as well. This is what makes people put their trust in the product. AQUA is without a doubt a giant bottled water brand, but the question now is, will the consumer have the interest to buy AQUALife? Purchase Intention is an activity that will appear after consumers do an evaluation to the alternatives given¹⁰. Consumers' activity in buying a product surely has gone through the process of purchase intention itself. So we can say that the purchase intentions of people living in the area where AQUA are available are really high to the point of creating a big gap of 46.7% dominance in the bottled water competition. In this

research, purchase intention is used to determine the success rate of green marketing implementation done by AQUA with their product AQUALife. Will the consumers' buying interest improve with this product or will it just stay the same?

A pre-research activity will be done prior to the main research. This pre-research will be done towards green brand knowledge possessed by people living in Bali and Bandung towards the term purchase intention using questionnaires. People from Bali were chosen as AQUALife was first launched there. On the other hand the people from Bandung were chosen because the area itself is considered one of the biggest and advanced cities in Indonesia. For each area a total of 20 respondents will be taken for the research.

On the brand awareness side, AQUALife is leading for the people living in Bali compared to the one in Bandung. At least, 55% respondents from Bali have known or seen the product AQUALife and also know where the products are being sold. On the other hand, people from Bandung only know the existence of AQUALife without knowing anything else. So with that in mind in terms of brand image owned by AQUA, at least 40% of people from Bali and 55% people from Bandung agree that AQUA has a really good quality. According to 30% of people living in Bali and 25% living in Bandung, AQUA is a brand that cares a lot about the environment. This shows that people from Bali and Bandung have a rather low rate of concern in terms of resolving environmental problems.

We can conclude that the rate of brand awareness to AQUALife in areas where the products are available such as Bali are considerably much higher than the areas where the products are not available such as Bandung. Only around 55% out of the 20 respondents from Bandung knows about AQUALife, only around 10% in difference with the people in Bali. This clearly shows that the products themselves do not pull up a lot of interest even to the people in Bali, even though the products themselves help solve a lot of plastic waste problems.

Brand image itself is seen from the importance of the product in terms of daily life usage for the people in Bali and Bandung which have different kinds of daily activities and culture. For the respondents in Bali, only 20% out of 20 respondents felt that AQUA can't be separated from their daily life. Bandung on the other hand reaches the rate of 60% out of 20 respondents that thinks that AQUA plays a valuable role in their daily life. AQUA as the main source of plastic waste problems are widely more accepted by the people in Bandung reaching 55% out of the respondents. Compared to the respondents from Bali, only 5% of respondents agree with the previous statement. So clearly there is a big difference in the brand image from AQUA as the main source of the plastic waste problem.

Purchase intentions possessed by the respondents from Bali reached the rate of 85% out of 20 respondents, a slight 5% less rate from the purchase intention rate possessed by the people from Bandung that scored 90%. So we can conclude that green marketing that was done by AQUA with the launch of AQUALife has a significant effect on the purchase intention rate from the people living in Bali and Bandung.

Literature Review

Green marketing

Every marketing activity for any products and services that pays attention and cares a lot towards the sustainability of the environment can be considered as green marketing. This type of marketing strategy is now being called upon to do by a lot of companies competing in the era where environmental problems are common. To put it simply, green marketing can be defined as the development and promotion of products that are being produced by decreasing their negative effects on the environment. Green marketing can also be defined as a form of study towards all efforts to consume, produce, distribute, promote, pack and admit the product with the sense of care and actively responding to the current environmental problems¹¹. The other may define green marketing as the application of a marketing device to facilitate the exchange that will satisfy the objectives of organizations or personal needs inside a preservation, protection, and conservation of the environment¹². There aren't many differences yet that could be learned from green marketing and the other marketing acts as the green marketing theory itself have not reached their deepest understanding. In their practice, green marketing still uses the general marketing theory.

Green Brand Knowledge

The knowledge about brands will be the first step for consumers towards buying a product. The feeling of knowing towards a brand could raise trust and comfort to the future buyer of the product. The bigger the knowledge towards the brand, the more consumers will feel safe and comfortable using those products.

Green brand knowledge can also be defined as the green brand module inside consumer's memory that is combined with a lot of association of commitment towards the environment¹⁰. On the other hand, according to Kotler, brand knowledge can be defined as the idea of the feeling, visual, experience, and trust that are all related to the brand itself. So a brand should have a strong, fun and unique relationship with the consumer.

Brand knowledge can also be defined as an associative network memory model, in a sense of a network of everything related to the brand inside the consumer's memory¹³. Everything that the consumers see and feel with other things that contains the information about a brand will be the creation of brand knowledge planted inside the consumer's memory and mind. Brand knowledge itself is divided into two components which are, brand awareness and brand image.

Brand Awareness

Consumers will consider buying a product when they are aware of the existence of the product itself. They don't need the experience of buying it or perhaps see it first to be able to create the intention of buying the products. As long as the consumer knows there are options to buy the product then they will consider buying it themselves. The high rate of brand awareness possessed by a product will simplify consumers to decide on making those products an option to buy. Brand awareness is said to be the possibility of consumer to recognize and know the availability and the step to get the products or services from the company¹⁴.

Brand awareness itself will appear the moment consumers realize the existence of the brand itself. Brand awareness combined with a strong visual association will encourage consumers to create the brand image of that brand¹⁵.

According to Keller¹³, brand awareness itself is divided into two things which are brand recognition and brand recall. Brand recognition is the consumer's ability to further know the specified brand even though they have known others before. Brand recall on the other hand can be defined as the consumer's ability to remember the specified brand at the time they are encountered with a category of product or the product that will satisfy their need or maybe when encountered with something that they need to buy.

It can be concluded that brand awareness is the consumer's ability in realizing the existence of a product, knowing how to acquire it, and making that specified brand as something that they will always think of when encountering their needs.

Brand Image

Buying a product or service with a good brand image in other people's perspective will make the consumer more certain with their decision. A good brand image will also make consumers consider other possible products. The reputation of the brand combined with promising factors and also other complimentary things from a product will then create the brand image¹⁵.

Brand image could be defined as the perception and option from consumers towards a brand which is visualized into various brand associations that are captured inside consumers mind¹⁶.

According to Keller¹³ back in 2013, a brand image needs associated activities that consist of strong connection, likeable, and unique aspects towards the brand inside consumers mind. Brand image itself consisted of brand attributes and brand benefits. Brand attributes are characteristics that describe the character of a product or service. Brand benefit on the other hand is a personal value that is sticking by its own by consumers towards products or services complementary.

Purchase Intention

When carrying out purchase intention activities, consumers will use five deciding sub-points which are brand, seller, sum, time, and paying methods¹⁰. A consumer's purchase intention depends on their satisfactory level of what they think they will get from the products and what comes in reality. If the brand could give satisfaction to that consumer, then that consumer will become a regular and won't be having a negative brand image towards that brand¹⁷.

Purchase intention from a consumer depends on the brand awareness towards that particular brand¹⁸. This shows that the purchase intention of a consumer is highly influenced by the knowledge of the brand that they know. Consumers are somehow reluctant on deciding to buy a product if they didn't know anything about the brand first. According to Ferdinand in NST¹⁹, purchase intention have four indicators which are: transactional interest (consumer willingness to buy a product); referential interest (consumer willingness to give

reference about the product to other people); preferential interest (consumer’s characteristic to have a main preference to a product); and explorative interest (consumer who wanted to look for information about a specified product, be it only that product or other elements that are associated to that product).

So we can conclude that purchase intention is an activity that appears after consumers have the brand awareness towards a product and feel satisfied towards the product that they have been using. Purchase intention can be measured using four indicators which are transactional interest, reference interest, preference interest, and explorative interest owned by consumers.

Materials and methods

This research is using a quantitative based method. The gathering of primary data for this research is gathered by handing out questionnaires in the form of *google form* to 100 respondents from Bandung and 100 respondents from Bali. The population for this research will come from the people living in Bali and Bandung. The calculation of data gathered will be done using the Likert scale. The Likert scale itself is an interval scale that specifically uses five measurements points which are strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree, and strongly disagree²⁰. In using the Likert scale, every measurement point will have the following value which are: Strongly agree - 5; agree - 4; undecided - 3, disagree - 2; strongly disagree - 1.

Variable	Dimension	Statement
Brand Knowledge	Brand Awareness ^{21,22,23,24}	1. I can quickly remember AQUALife’s symbol or logo 2. I am able to recognize AQUALife’s water bottled brand compared to other brand 3. I have heard AQUALife’s water bottled brand 4. I have received information that AQUALife is committed to preserving the environment. 5. I know that AQUALife is an environmentally friendly product 6. I realize that using an environmentally friendly product gives out long term benefits to me and the environment itself 7. AQUALife is the first brand that showed up in my memory when I’m talking about environmentally friendly bottled water.

	Brand Image ^{16,21,23,24}	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. AQUALife has a good reputation 2. AQUALife has a good quality 3. AQUALife is a safe to consume product 4. AQUALife brand has an interesting design 5. AQUALife's functions are suitable to my needs and hopes 6. AQUALife makes me pay attention more to the environment 7. AQUALife's packaging are made by using recyclable materials 8. Based on my view, AQUALife plays the role in preserving the environment 9. AQUALife can be the inspiration towards environmental problem, especially plastic waste problem
Purchase Intention ^{19, 22, 24}		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. I want to buy AQUALife 2. I have intention to buy AQUALife as a form of my concern towards the environment 3. I'm going to choose AQUALife instead of other brands 4. I'm willing to pay in higher price for AQUALife instead of other brands 5. I will recommend AQUALife to my relatives/friends/other people 6. I will recommend AQUALife to be used in big scale event 7. I want to find information about AQUALife (availability, price, etc) 8. I want to find more information about how AQUALife could play the role of decreasing plastic waste

Research Results Respondents Profile

Both Bandung and Bali respondents ranged between the ages of 19 to 21 years old. Both areas of respondents are paying attention to the environment by bringing their own tumblr bottle. There are at least 61% respondents from Bandung and 72% respondents from Bali that prefer to bring their own tumblr or personal water bottle. It is also shown that buying bottled water is somehow considered not relevant to their daily lives.

Results Validity test results

In doing the validity test, the researcher is using the Pearson Correlation method. The numbers of respondents that are being tested for the validity test in this research are 40 respondents coming from Bandung and Bali. Based on the distribution table with N=40, and the significance rate of 5% then the value of r-table is 0.312. To determine the validity of the questionnaire statement the calculation should have the value bigger than 0.312 in order to be labelled as valid.

No	Variable	Validity Correlation	
		Bandung	Bali
1	Brand	0.750	0.722
2	Knowledge	0.749	0.690

3		0.726	0.823
4		0.822	0.772
5		0.693	0.826
6		0.517	0.644
7		0.750	0.767
8		0.802	0.859
9		0.796	0.836
10		0.771	0.863
11		0.577	0.854
12		0.836	0.895
13		0.702	0.865
14		0.779	0.808
15		0.645	0.868
16		0.681	0.832
17	Purchase Intention	0.423	0.716
18		0.507	0.792
19		0.700	0.731
20		0.370	0.652
21		0.699	0.755
22		0.604	0.825
23		0.447	0.681
24		0.358	0.759

Reliability test results

In doing the reliability test, the researcher is using the Alpha-Cronbach's method. The questionnaires will be labelled as reliable when the value is bigger than 0,60.

Variabel	Alpha Cronbach's Bandung	Bali
Brand Knowledge	0.942	0.967
Purchase Intention	0.806	0.934

Correlation test results

The method used to do the analysis is the Pearson Product Moment. This correlation analysis has the objective of measuring the relation value between the dependent variable with the independent variable.

The test results for the respondents coming from Bandung shows a value of 0,797. According to Pearson's r table, the value 0,797 stands in a high level of relationship. This shows that green brand knowledge and purchase intention has a really strong connection to the respondents from Bandung.

On the other hand, the results for respondents living in Bali shows the value number of 0.807. Based on Pearson's r table, the value 0.807 stands in a high level of relationship. So we can also conclude that the connection between green brand knowledge and purchase intention to the respondents from Bali.

Hypothesis test results

The testing process of hypothesis in this research uses the value of the t-table. Based on the test results

done towards the two respondents coming from Bandung and Bali with the value number of 13,051 and 13,546. So we can conclude that the green brand knowledge variable that consists of brand awareness and brand image has a positive effect on the purchase intention of the AQUALife product.

Analysis

Following the current situation, whereas AQUALife being only available in Bali, means that the product brand awareness towards the respondents from Bandung score much lower to the respondents from Bali. These results can be proven by showing the results of respondents from Bandung who knew less information about the AQUALife product. However, the respondents from Bandung are aware of environmentally friendly products having long term benefits. On the other hand the respondents from Bali are more aware of the existence of AQUALife even though not being at a high level of awareness. This could be said remembering the fact that AQUALife is a newly launched exclusive product. Therefore, it can be concluded that AQUALife is lacking brand awareness.

Overall, the brand image owned by AQUALife towards the respondents from Bandung as well as Bali are at a good level. This could be affected by the AQUALife brand name itself, meaning that name AQUA still plays a big role in the process. As AQUA itself still has a big and strong brand impression to the society. As mentioned before the AQUA brand alone dominates at least 46.7% of the current bottled water market. Therefore the AQUALife brand itself which is still related to the AQUA brand will have a better chance of getting a strong brand image. moreover AQUA also participate in doing CSR activities which focuses on preserving the environment such as providing clean water to remote areas.

Overall, the purchase intention level of the respondents from Bandung are considered pretty good whereas for the respondents from Bali the level is considered good. It can also be said that both areas won't buy the AQUALife product as it is much more expensive compared to the regular variant of AQUA. This decision was made knowing that AQUALife provides more benefits to the environment compared to the regular AQUA even though it has the same content of mineral water. They might buy or have the intention to buy AQUALife but not because of the reason behind the product objectives. In any case, the respondents from Bali will more likely to buy the AQUALife product to help the environment rather than the respondents from Bandung.

Conclusion

The measurements for the green brand knowledge can be seen from the dimension aspects of brand awareness and brand image. The brand awareness dimension possessed by the respondents from Bandung towards the AQUALife product can be said to be at a pretty good level. This shows that the people from Bandung have put much attention to the AQUALife product even though the product itself is not available in that area. For the brand image dimension, the people of Bandung have a good image towards the AQUALife product. This being said even though the people from Bandung don't feel that using the AQUALife product will make them care more about the environment. The brand image possessed by the people from Bandung could

be said at a good level, this is because the AQUALife itself is still under the good impression of the AQUA which already have a good and strong impression in the societies. On the other hand, the brand awareness dimension owned by the people from Bali used to measure the green brand knowledge can be said at a good level. This statement is aligned with the situation where the AQUALife products are available in the area. However, even though the products are available all over Bali, most of the people from Bali are not able to remember the AQUALife product. In terms of brand image aspects, the people from Bali have proven to have a good image towards the AQUALife products. AQUALife is viewed as an environmentally friendly product and is encouraging people to pay more attention to the environment. Overall it can be said that the green brand knowledge owned by the people from Bali is at a good level. Aligned with the reasoning behind AQUA's higher up when picking Bali as the location for the AQUALife product launch. It is for the reason that Bali viewed as an area which is more open to environmental change process.

In terms of the purchase intention possessed by the people from Bandung can be said as fairly good. With the current level of green brand knowledge possessed by the people from Bandung, it is now safe to say that it could cause the intention of buying the AQUALife product. On the other hand, the level of purchase intention possessed by the people from Bali is at a good level, also with a good level of intention towards buying the AQUALife product. However, for the people from Bandung, the intention to buy AQUALife products is not based on the interest of preserving the environment. This is caused by the people from Bandung mainly thinking that AQUALife is actually not trying to solve the plastic waste problem. The people from Bali on the other hand think the opposite way whereas they think the AQUALife product is trying to solve the plastic waste problem. The people from Bandung don't have the intention to recommend AQUALife, this can be caused because the people from that area haven't got the chance to experience the benefits directly. Other than that, the people from Bandung also doesn't have the capabilities to buy the product since it is not available in the area they are living in.

After comparing and analyzing the data and test results between the respondents from Bandung and Bali, it is shown that there are no significant differences between the two. We can now conclude that the green marketing done by AQUA doesn't really affect the green brand knowledge possessed by the people from Bandung and Bali. That being said, the brand image owned by AQUA is still standing in a really good position. This can be caused by the habit of most people from Bandung and Bali where they are used to bringing and use their own tumblr or water bottle for daily usage.

In terms of the green marketing which was done by AQUA towards AQUALife, the results are shown to be less effective. With the situation in Bali where AQUALife is widely available throughout the area, the green brand knowledge towards the brand itself is considered rather bad. This level of green brand knowledge doesn't go too far with the respondents from Bandung where the product itself is not available in the area. The people from Bandung mainly think that buying the AQUALife product is basically to fulfil the need of the people towards bottled water, and not based on the purpose of the environment preserving campaign. This statement can be caused by the AQUALife product being unavailable in Bandung and the people are mainly

not care much about the environment itself.

Recommendations

The first recommendation to be made is actually for AQUALife to launch the product in Bandung. Based on the research done, most of the people from Bandung have a fairly good purchase intention. Prior to the launch, it is encouraged for AQUALife to increase the information that is going to be shared to the future consumers. It can be seen that the people from Bandung are lacking information towards the product. AQUALife could further display the raw materials and production process in the most effective way possible. The brand awareness possessed by AQUALife itself can be considered as pretty low be it for the people from Bandung or Bali. The launch of AQUALife in Bandung should be done as soon as possible. After seeing the people's habit of using and bringing their own tumblr or bottled water for daily usage, the rate of people doing this reached the number of 61%. This data showed that there has been a shifting in terms of habits from the people of Bandung. Before the people fully shift, AQUALife should be launched as soon as possible to maintain the image of AQUA itself.

Based on the respondents' profile coming from Bandung and Bali that reach the rate of 61% and 72% of bringing their own tumblr, AQUALife is better on making another environmentally friendly product other than the AQUALife. This is because bottled water is somehow insignificant in the daily lives of respondents from Bandung and Bali. AQUA could create a vending machine that sells refill water for tumblr or the people's owned water bottle. This vending machine could also have the option of milliliter contents that are going to be pick by the people itself.

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